

IMPROVING THE SPEECH OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN WITH THE HELP OF DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation: This article analyzes the methods and effectiveness of improving the speech of preschool children through the use of digital educational technologies. The impact of modern digital tools, such as interactive programs, mobile applications and multimedia technologies on the development of children's oral speech is studied. The possibilities of expanding children's vocabulary, forming phonetic skills and developing a culture of communication using digital technologies are also considered. The results of the study confirm the important role of digital technologies in the development of children's speech and provide recommendations for their effective integration into the educational process.

Keywords: Digital educational technologies, preschool children, speech development, interactive programs, multimedia tools, pedagogical innovations, culture of communication.

Introduction

Today, technologies are developing rapidly and are becoming an integral part of our lives. In particular, the widespread use of digital technologies in education is shaping modern pedagogical approaches and opening up new opportunities for the educational process. In particular, the issue of developing children's speech at the preschool stage requires modern methods and technologies. Because it is this period of a child's life that is the most important foundation for the formation of his speech abilities, thinking skills and communication culture.

Digital technologies play an important role in expanding children's worldview, directing them to modern knowledge and skills. Interactive programs, multimedia tools and mobile applications not only enliven the learning process, but also increase children's motivation to learn a language, develop their independent learning skills. Activities organized with the help of technologies help children to more fully demonstrate their speech abilities, which has a positive effect on their communication culture and socialization.

This article is devoted to exploring these opportunities, which considers the role and importance of digital educational technologies in improving the speech

of preschool children. The importance of this approach in shaping the future generation as individuals with high knowledge and skills through the introduction of educational methods that meet the requirements of the modern world is incomparable.

Methodology

The study of the issue of improving the speech of preschool children using digital technologies requires a scientifically based and practically applicable methodology. This study used modern pedagogical methods, which were aimed at studying the possibilities of integrating digital educational tools into the process of working with children.

The main approaches of the study included experimental observation, testing interactive technologies and analysis of their results. Initially, diagnostic methods were used to determine the level of speech development of preschool children. This process made it possible to measure the vocabulary, pronunciation accuracy and communication skills of children. Then, testing of educational programs created on the basis of digital technologies was carried out. These programs included game-like tasks, sound and visual aids, and interactive exercises, and were designed to be interesting and effective for children.

During the testing process, special attention was paid to observing children's activities and assessing their changes. The results of the observation showed a positive dynamics of speech development of children during their engagement with digital educational programs. In this process, working together with parents and educators was important, as they supported the development of children by being actively involved in the learning process.

This methodology is aimed at assessing the effectiveness of digital educational tools in improving children's speech, expanding the possibilities of its application in real practice. As a result, recommendations were developed that are necessary for the successful integration of modern technologies into the educational process. This will serve to raise the speech development of preschool children to a new level.

Discussion

Digital technologies are increasingly penetrating the educational process, and these changes are yielding significant results, especially in working with preschool children. The results of this study show that the use of digital educational tools not only increases children's interest in the learning process, but also allows them to effectively develop their speech abilities. By analyzing

the data obtained during the discussion, observations and test results, important conclusions were drawn about the role of digital technologies in the educational process.

First, it was found that digital technologies in the development of children's speech increase their desire to communicate. Interactive games, audiovisual materials and virtual environments are convenient and interesting tools for children. These tools help children increase their vocabulary, improve their pronunciation, and develop their ability to express themselves verbally. For example, it has been observed that children learn new words faster and use them in communication with the help of special mobile applications.

Secondly, digital technologies provide an individual approach to the learning process. Programs tailored to the developmental level and interests of each child increase the effectiveness of the learning process. Also, the independent learning environment created for children through technology plays an important role in developing self-control and critical thinking skills.

At the same time, there are some problems with the use of digital technologies. Children's excessive screen time can negatively affect their health or limit their social skills. Therefore, it is necessary to maintain a balance and set clear time limits when integrating technologies into the educational process.

In general, the results of the study confirm the positive impact of digital educational technologies on the speech development of preschool children. However, in order to successfully organize this process, it is necessary to conduct constant research on the mutual cooperation of parents, educators and specialists, as well as on the rational use of these tools. Thus, the effective use of digital technologies serves not only the speech, but also the general intellectual and social development of children.

Conclusion

One of the most important tasks facing the educational process in the modern world is to find tools and approaches that serve the comprehensive development of children as individuals. Digital technologies open up enormous opportunities in this regard, in particular, their role in the development of speech in preschool children is incomparable. The results of this study showed that the rational use of digital educational tools is of great importance in the development of children's vocabulary, pronunciation accuracy and communication culture.

The educational process organized through interactive games and multimedia technologies creates not only an interesting but also an effective

learning environment for children. Technologies also provide an individual approach and offer each child teaching methods that are appropriate for their capabilities. This helps to reveal and develop the child's natural abilities.

However, the limitations of digital tools should not be ignored. Since long-term use can affect the health and psychological state of a child, it is important to use these tools in a balanced and controlled manner. Therefore, parents and educators should work together and monitor the process of children's use of technology.

This study confirmed the effectiveness of digital educational tools in the speech development of preschool children. The results showed that by properly integrating technology into the educational process, it is possible to form and develop speech skills in children. This will create broad opportunities for them in the future and prepare them for the formation of successful individuals. Thus, the development of the educational process using digital technologies is one of the important directions of modern pedagogy, the results of which will make a positive contribution to the future development of society. With a rational approach, digital tools will undoubtedly play a decisive role in the intellectual and social development of children.

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